

Prevalence and hematological alterations in goats suffering from selected blood borne protozoan diseases

Ghazanfar Hussain¹, Farman Ali², Khurram Ashfaq^{3*}, Sanober⁴, Zahra Fatima⁵, Saifuddin⁶, Yousef Abdal Jalil Fadladdin^{7*}

¹Institute of Feed Research, Graduate School of Chinese Academy of Agricultural Sciences, Beijing, China.

²Institute of Animal and Dairy Science, Faculty of Animal Husbandry, University of Agriculture, Faisalabad, Pakistan.

³Department of Clinical Medicine and Surgery, University of Agriculture, Faisalabad, Pakistan.

⁴Department of Animal Biotechnology, Dankook University, Cheonan, South Korea.

⁵University of Agriculture, Faisalabad, Pakistan.

⁶Institute of Microbiology, University of Agriculture, Faisalabad, Pakistan.

⁷Department of Biological Sciences, Faculty of Sciences, King Abdulaziz University, Jeddah, Saudi Arabia

*Corresponding authors: drkhurramashfaq33@gmail.com; yfadladdin@kau.edu.sa

Abstract

Anaplasmosis is a widespread tick-borne rickettsial disease responsible for fever, weakness, dyspnea and progressive anemia in small ruminants, including sheep and goats. An emerging infectious disease caused by *Anaplasma capra* and mainly transmitted through infected ticks to susceptible hosts during blood feeding. These pathogens are particularly devastating to goat herds in Pakistan, resulting a significant economic losses. However, limited information are available on the epidemiology of *Anaplasma* spp. among small ruminants in some parts of Pakistan. The study aimed to estimate the prevalence of anaplasmosis to unravel the association of potential risk factors and to investigate the effect on hematological parameters in affected goats compare with healthy goats. A total of 384 blood samples randomly collected were initially screened microscopically and then subjected to PCR targeting the amplification of the *16S rRNA* gene fragment of *Anaplasma*. The PCR-based positive samples were then processed for sequencing. The positive strong bands that were achieved from gel electrophoresis were sent for DNA sequencing, for the molecular confirmation up to species level and infer phylogeny. Phylogenetic tree was constructed by using MEGA software after the sequencing. The statistical analysis of microscopic examination was carried out by the Chi-square test with significance of association ($p < 0.05$) between different variables using statistix 10 and graph pad version. For the hematological results student's t-test was used to find Mean \pm SEM. The hematological analysis of infected goats showed that, there was a significant decrease in the mean value of red blood cells, hemoglobin, white blood cells, lymphocytes, HCT, GRAN and GRA%, while significantly increase in mean value of mean corpuscular volume (MCV), mean corpuscular hemoglobin (MCH) and LYM%. *Anaplasma* spp. infection is a serious health problem in small ruminants and this is the first study focused on quantifying prevalence in goats. Further studies are needed to enhance the understanding of factors related to the disease, which can help design new methods for anaplasmosis control in livestock.

Keywords: *Anaplasma*, goats, blood picture, molecular detection